

Table S1. Oligonucleotides used in this study.

Name	Sequence	Application
<i>AndhB</i>	GTCGTTGCTTTTCTTTCTG	Northern
<i>AT7ndhB</i>	TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAAATATAGGCCTGCCT	Northern
<i>aadAfw1</i>	GGAAACTTCGGCTTCCCCTGG	Northern, sequencing
<i>aadAT7</i>	GTAATCGACTCACTATAGGGAACCGGATCAAAGAGT	Northern
<i>HVP16B_forward</i>	ATGGACCTGGACCTGGAATG	Northern, sequencing
<i>T7 HVP16B_reverse</i>	TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGCTCTTCTACTTCTACTCCT	Northern
<i>HVP182_forward</i>	CTGCTGGAGGAGGAAATAAAC	Northern, sequencing
<i>T7 HVP182_reverse</i>	TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGGCAGGAGCACATCCTAAAAT AC	Northern
<i>mR21</i>	AGAACGTGGGTCTCCAAAAC	Southern
<i>mR35</i>	TGGAATCGTGTTAGGTCTAATTCC	Southern
<i>bbfor</i>	GATTTGTCGACATCAAGTTCG	cloning
<i>bbrev</i>	ACAGGAGGACGTTTCGTTTGC	cloning
<i>pHVP16rev</i>	TTATTACAAGCTGGATTA AAAAGC	cloning; genotyping; sequencing
<i>pHVP18rev</i>	AAGCTGGATTAAGAAGAAAACC	cloning; genotyping; sequencing
<i>aadoutrev</i>	ACTGCGGAGCCGTACAAATG	sequencing